

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-296-IC-10% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230404
Vial:	58	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	4 296
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	273.0nm
Run Time:	35.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 273.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	4/4/2023 12:36:46 PM CST		
Date Processed:	4/12/2023 10:07:38 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	16.607	174299	43.60	6491
2	18.043	177174	44.32	6060
3	22.579	24142	6.04	663
4	27.706	24165	6.04	555

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-297-IC-10% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230404
Vial:	59	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	4 297
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	273.0nm
Run Time:	35.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 273.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	4/4/2023 1:12:26 PM CST		
Date Processed:	4/12/2023 10:10:56 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	16.662	696	0.06	71
2	18.162	1124924	99.62	37232
3	22.647	2003	0.18	91
4	27.939	1581	0.14	107